

Chemical Recycling: A Sustainable Solution for Plastic Waste Management

Anas Jamil Abdulrahman¹, Azd Zayoud^{1,2}, Marvin Kusenber¹, Kevin M. Van Geem^{1,*}

¹ Laboratory for Chemical Technology (LCT), Department of Materials, Textiles and Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering & Architecture, Ghent University, B-9052 Zwijnaarde, Belgium

² Pryme NV, 3065 Rotterdam, The Netherlands

*Corresponding author: Kevin.VanGeem@UGent.be

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Abstract

The accumulation of plastic waste constitutes a growing global challenge, highlighting the critical role of recycling in waste management. Despite the fact that, the mechanical recycling is one of the most common and well established plastic recycling methods, however, it struggles with mixed, contaminated, or degraded plastic waste. Chemical recycling can complement mechanical recycling by processing hard-to-recycle mechanically plastic waste to close this gap by converting waste plastics into feedstocks for the production of virgin-quality plastics and chemicals. This white paper outlines key technologies, benefits, challenges, and market trends, and assesses the role of chemical recycling in a circular, low-carbon plastics economy.

1. Introduction

Plastics have revolutionized modern life, offering convenience, durability, and versatility. However, massive plastic production is leading to a massive growing waste crisis in landfills, oceans, and ecosystems worldwide. Traditional mechanical recycling works effectively for clean, homogeneous waste plastic streams but it struggles with mixed, contaminated, or complex waste plastic streams. Moreover, mechanical recycling down grade the quality of recycled plastic with each cycle, limiting reuse potential. Addressing these gaps requires innovative solutions, including chemical recycling.

2. Principles of chemical recycling

Chemical recycling breaks plastics down into their fundamental chemical building blocks, unlike mechanical recycling, which involves melting and reprocessing waste plastic streams,. Chemical recycling enables the production of high-purity feedstock that can be processed into virgin-quality plastics, offering a closed-loop solution for hard-to-recycle waste plastics. Chemical recycling encompasses a range of technologies that can be classified into two main categories based on their material recovery pathways:

- Closed-loop recycling (monomer/oligomer recovery): This approach breaks down the waste plastics into oligomers and monomers, which can be repolymerized into virgin-quality plastics, maintaining material circularity.

- **Open-loop recycling (feedstock recycling):** In this route, plastics are broken down into chemical feedstocks such as hydrocarbons or syngas, which are used in broader chemical processes, rather than directly regenerated into the same type of plastic. Open-loop recycling is more tolerant of mixed and contaminated plastics.

Regardless of the specific pathway, most chemical recycling technologies follow a core sequence: (1) breakdown of plastic waste into simpler chemical compounds, (2) recovery and purification of the resulting intermediates, such as monomers, hydrocarbons, or syngas, and (3) conversion into valuable chemical products, including virgin-quality plastics and/or chemical feedstocks. The efficiency and sustainability of each step depend on the plastic feedstock, contamination, and the technology employed, highlighting the importance of tailored approaches for different waste streams.

2.1 Breakdown of plastic waste:

A. Thermal cracking:

- **Pyrolysis:** plastics are heated and broken down in the absence of oxygen to produce liquid hydrocarbons, plus gases and chars, in the absence of oxygen. Suitable mainly for sorted polyolefins, it can also process some mixed, low-contamination waste. Operating at 400–600 °C, it preserves hydrocarbon chains for upgrading (e.g., via steam cracking) into olefins. Variants include hydrolysis, catalytic pyrolysis, and hydrothermal liquefaction. Key drawbacks include high energy consumption, sensitivity to contamination, and scaling challenges.
- **Gasification:** Gasification occurs at higher temperatures (700–1200 °C) in a controlled oxygen environment, converting plastics into syngas (mainly H₂ and CO). The syngas can be utilized via synthesis routes, such as the Fischer–Tropsch process, to produce hydrocarbons for new plastic production. Unlike pyrolysis, gasification is well-suited for heavily contaminated plastic wastes, requires fewer process steps, and offers broad chemical integration. Still, it demands more energy than pyrolysis and involves larger-scale, more complex infrastructure.

- B. **Depolymerization:** Depolymerization is a process that breaks down complex polymer chains into their original monomers or oligomers using combinations of heat and

chemistry (chemolysis), or solvents (solvolysis). Depolymerization is particularly suitable for condensation polymers such as PET and polyamides. It is commonly carried out through solvolysis-based methods, including hydrolysis (the most established approach), glycolysis, methanolysis, and aminolysis.

C. Enzymatic and Biological Methods (emerging technologies): Certain enzymes or microorganisms can selectively depolymerize plastics such as PET or polyurethane into monomers. While currently limited to laboratory or pilot-scale applications, enzymatic recycling offers high specificity and low energy requirements, with minimal environmental emissions.

2.2 Recovery and purification

Following the breakdown of plastic waste into intermediates, e.g. monomers, oligomers and hydrocarbons, the resulting products must be separated and purified to meet the required quality specifications for the existing chemical or polymer production systems. The efficiency of this step is critical: inadequate separation and/or purification can compromise the performance of recycled materials and limit their integration into existing industrial processes.

2.3 Conversion into new plastics and chemicals

Once purified, the intermediates can be converted into valuable chemical products or plastics through chemical synthesis. Monomers recovered from closed-loop processes can be re-polymerized into virgin-quality plastics, effectively closing the material loop. Hydrocarbons generated from open-loop processes, such as pyrolysis oils or syngas, can be further processed, e.g. steam cracking, into olefins and other chemical feedstocks for producing new plastics. By enabling the transformation of waste into high-value materials, chemical recycling supports both circularity and resource efficiency in the plastics industry.

3. Opportunities & challenges of chemical recycling

3.1 Opportunities of chemical recycling

Chemical recycling offers numerous advantages in the context of plastic waste management and sustainability:

- **Processing complex waste streams:** A significant advantage of chemical recycling is its ability to process plastic waste that is not suitable for mechanical recycling. This includes mixed, contaminated plastics, which can be challenging to recycle mechanically.
- **Creating new feedstocks:** Chemical recycling bridges the gap between waste management and the petrochemical industry. The process converts waste into feedstock, such as pyrolysis oil, that can be used to produce virgin-quality plastics and chemicals.
- **Technological innovation and economic growth:** The chemical recycling industry is growing, with a significant number of operational and planned plants. This growth presents opportunities for investment, technological development, and job creation.
- **Lower carbon footprint:** By using recycled feedstock, chemical recycling can significantly lower the carbon footprint of plastic production, helping to mitigate climate change.
- **Circular economy and material circularity:** Closed-loop processes can regenerate virgin-quality plastics, preserving material value and enabling multiple life cycles. Open-loop processes provide flexibility in converting hard-to-recycle plastics into chemicals or fuels, supporting a broader circular economy.
- **Complementing waste management infrastructure:** Chemical recycling supports regulatory targets for plastic recycling, Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes, and corporate environmental, social and governance (ESG) initiatives. Companies can leverage chemical recycling to meet sustainability reporting standards and achieve circular economy commitments.

3.2 Challenges and considerations in chemical recycling

Despite its potential, chemical recycling faces several challenges that need to be addressed for the successful scaling and implementation of chemical recycling:

- **Pre-processing requirements:** One major challenge is the need for consistent and well-sorted feedstock. Chemical plants are not designed to handle heterogeneous solid inputs, which can cause operational issues. Therefore, pre-processing of waste, including sorting, separation, cleaning, and resizing, is essential to ensure a continuous and reliable chemical recycling process.

- **Integration with existing petrochemical infrastructure:** Incorporating pyrolysis-derived oils and waxes into refineries faces hurdles from product variability, contaminants, and processing incompatibilities, hindering large-scale adoption.
- **Economic and financial hurdles:** Chemical recycling processes can be more expensive than mechanical recycling, requiring significant capital investment in large-scale infrastructure and technologies. Clear long-term plans and policies are needed to create a stable investment climate and incentivize the development of new techniques (RVO, 2024).
- **Strategic recycling:** chemical recycling is not a replacement for mechanical recycling but rather complements it. A key consideration is ensuring that plastic waste streams that can be economically and effectively recycled by mechanical means are not diverted to chemical recycling. Optimal recycling technology should be determined based on a complete lifecycle assessment, considering costs, environmental impact, and the quality of the output.
- **Environmental Impact:** While chemical recycling has a more positive environmental profile than landfilling and incineration, chemical recycling is energy-intensive and can generate hazardous emissions or byproducts. To mitigate these challenges, it's essential to use clean energy sources and technologies and maintain rigorous environmental controls.
- **Policies and regulatory frameworks consideration:** Policies are needed to guide the industry, ensuring that chemical recycling contributes to a genuinely circular and low-carbon economy. Clear and consistent regulatory frameworks are required to define chemical recycling and establish appropriate environmental standards, such as mass balance accounting.
- **Public Perception and Transparency:** There is ongoing debate and scrutiny regarding the actual environmental benefits and potential risks of chemical recycling. Transparency in operations, environmental performance data, and independent life cycle assessments are vital to building public trust.

4. Recent advancements

Chemical recycling is evolving rapidly, with research and development efforts focused on enhancing efficiency, reducing costs, and minimizing environmental impacts. These trends are expected to continue, with key prospects outlined below:

- **Technological maturation (current & recent):** Chemical recycling technologies—particularly pyrolysis, catalytic depolymerization, and solvent extraction—have advanced significantly in efficiency, selectivity, and feedstock flexibility. Pyrolysis plants are already scaling from 30–50 kt/year in 2021 toward 100 kt/year capacities by 2030 as demonstrated by ongoing industry deployments (RVO, 2024).
- **Integration with existing infrastructure (recent progress):** Several companies have successfully integrated pyrolysis oil and monomers into existing steam crackers and polymerization units, demonstrating compatibility with petrochemical infrastructure. Early mass-balance certified products (e.g., recycled polymers used in packaging) mark a key recent milestone.
- **Economic momentum & partnerships (recent):** Multiple demo and commercial-scale units have come online globally, attracting strategic partnerships between waste handlers, technology providers, and petrochemical companies. These collaborations are improving feedstock security and supply-chain reliability. Current projections indicate that combined mechanical and chemical recycling could treat 250 million tons of waste by 2060, generating \$300–400 billion in revenue (RVO, 2024).
- **Digitalization & AI in operations (recent):** Rapid advancements in AI-based sorting, robotics for material recovery, and machine-learning-guided process control are already improving feedstock purity and reducing operational downtime in newly commissioned plants.
- **Policy developments (recent):** Emerging EU and national frameworks are now explicitly defining chemical recycling, supporting mass-balance certification, and setting recycled-content targets. These recent regulatory clarifications are helping derisk investments and accelerate permitting (RVO, 2024).
- **Public awareness & social momentum (recent):** Increased consumer and stakeholder pressure regarding plastic pollution has created strong market demand for recycled-content products, boosting acceptance of chemically recycled materials.

- **Workforce development (early recent signals):** As new facilities begin operations, universities and technical institutes have started exploring specialized programs and training tracks related to polymer recycling, catalysis, and sustainable process engineering (RVO, 2024).

5. Chemical recycling technology landscape

The chemical recycling industry is on track for a tenfold capacity increase, from about one million tons in 2022 to 10 million tons by 2030 (Applied Market Information, 2025). Demonstration and commercial pyrolysis plants, mostly at TRL 7–9, process primarily mixed polyolefin waste. Plants' capacities are expected to more than double from 30–50 kta in 2021 to around 100 kta by 2030 (RVO, 2024). Key players include Wastewise, Plastic Energy, Petronas, Fuenix Ecogy, BlueAlps, and Pryme, working with off-takers such as SABIC, Dow, Neste, Borealis, and Shell to integrate pyrolysis oils into petrochemical refineries. Gasification-based technologies, operated commercially by Enerkem and Gidara Energy (TRL 9), convert plastic waste into syngas for upgrading into fuels and chemical feedstocks (RVO, 2024).

Recent developments in chemical recycling focus on processing contaminated waste streams that are challenging for conventional pyrolysis while aiming for high-value products. For example, Mura Technology's Hydro-PRS, at TRL 7–8, uses supercritical water liquefaction for wet or mixed plastics (Dow, 2022). Agilyx's TRL 9 non-catalytic pyrolysis treats oxygen- and halogen-containing plastics, incorporating contaminant removal to produce high-quality pyrolysis oils (Laird, 2023). ARCUS Greencycling, at TRL 7–8, employs pyrolysis for oxygen- and halogen-rich wastes (BASF, 2022), while BioBTX, also TRL 7–8, uses catalytic pyrolysis of plastics and biomass to produce high-selectivity BTX aromatics (BioBTX, 2024). Synova, at TRL 7–8, applies the MILENA gasification process to biowaste and polyolefins, integrating OLGA tar removal and Pure.rGas™ purification to produce cracker-ready gas (Synova, 2025). Depolymerization of PET is the most mature application of this technology (TRL 7–9, 50–110 kta capacity), with Loop Industries, Carbios, and Eastman as leading players. For polystyrene, depolymerization, as pursued by INEOS Styrolution, remains less mature (TRL 5–7) and underdevelopment.

The following research projects exemplify efforts to validate technologies through large-scale testing and to accelerate their commercial deployment in chemical recycling. eLECTRO (TRL 7) is a Horizon Europe-funded initiative involving 12 academic and industrial partners, aiming

to deliver electrified waste-to-olefins technologies integrated with downstream olefin and polyolefin production by 2026 (eLECTRO, 2022). MoReTec-1, supported by the EU Innovation Fund and led by LyondellBasell, targets TRL 7–8 with a planned 50 kta electrified chemical recycling facility scheduled to start in 2026 (Commission, 2023; LyondellBasell, 2024). The PULSE Project, led by Neste, will integrate a liquefied waste plastic processing unit into its existing Porvoo refinery (Neste, 2023). Finally, Mura Technology and Ghent University are developing a pilot-scale supercritical-water HTL unit to demonstrate Hydro-PRT® for hard-to-recycle plastics and composites, advancing the technology to TRL 6-7 (Mura, 2024).

6. Future outlook

- **Further industrial scale-up:** Chemical recycling is expected to expand to larger, more efficient continuous plants, improving feedstock flexibility and lowering costs. Modular systems and distributed processing hubs may emerge for regions with constrained logistics.
- **Enhanced process performance:** Future innovation will focus on low-energy depolymerization, advanced catalysts, enzymatic routes, co-processing with renewable hydrogen, and improved solvent recovery systems.
- **Deep integration with circular-economy frameworks:** Increased recycled-content mandates, extended producer responsibility (EPR), and harmonized global standards will reinforce chemical recycling's role alongside mechanical recycling.
- **Next-generation digitalization:** AI-based prediction of feedstock composition, autonomous process optimization, and digital twins of recycling plants will become mainstream.
- **Expanded workforce & education pathways:** As the industry scales, new jobs will emerge in plant operations, process design, catalyst development, waste logistics, and sustainability assessment.
- **Growing global acceptance:** With stronger regulations, improved technology performance, and increasing societal support, chemical recycling will become a core component of global plastic-waste management systems.

Conclusion

Chemical recycling supports mechanical recycling by converting plastics that are difficult to recycle into feedstocks for new materials, lessening our dependence on fossil resources and helping to achieve climate goals. However, achieving meaningful scale requires overcoming several systemic challenges. High-quality and consistent feedstock preparation, deployment of clean, efficient, and economically viable technologies, and seamless integration with existing petrochemical infrastructure are essential for reliable operation. Clear policies, consistent definitions, and transparent environmental data will be key to the reliability of chemical recycling. With continued technological innovation, strengthened regulatory support, and increased collaboration across the value chain, chemical recycling has the potential to become a core pillar of a circular, low-carbon plastics economy, complementing mechanical recycling and helping transition the plastics sector toward long-term sustainability.

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